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A time-dependent creep model for rock based on damage mechanics

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Abstract:

A creep model based on the damage mechanics is proposed in this study to describe the three-stage creep deformation of rocks under conventional triaxial loading conditions. The proposed model has a simple form as it is based on the mechanism which assumes that the time-dependent creep behavior of rocks is solely described by the damage evolution. Verification of the proposed model against the creep tests shows that the model can reflect the three-stage creep behavior under higher stress levels as well as the elastic behavior under lower stress levels using the same model equations. The features of the proposed model include: 1) Simple mathematical form as it contains only one strain component without strain partitioning, and one set of equations to predict the creep deformation for all stress levels; and 2) The model requires only four parameters. All these features make the proposed model simple to use and easy to implement.

Keywords: creep strain; damage mechanics; three-phase; strain partitioning

1. Introduction

Creep refers to the increase in deformation with time of geomaterials which are subjected to a constant stress smaller than the failure stress. In addition, geomaterials respond differently at different strain rates. Better understanding of the creep behavior of rocks is important to predict the long-term deformation of geological structures, such as landslides, tunnels, dams, and foundations, which are subjected to a long-term loading. Experimentally observed creep behavior of materials typically exhibits three stages (Fig. 1): 1) Primary creep, 2) Secondary creep, and 3) Tertiary creep, followed by failure (Lockner 1993; Main 2000; Wang 2004; Amitrano and Helmstetter 2006; Heap et al. 2009). The creep strain rate during the primary creep stage decays gradually with time. During secondary creep, the strain rate remains nearly constant. The strain rate during tertiary creep increases exponentially before rupture.

Fig. 1 Typical strain-time curve of rocks under different stages of creep.

Various approaches have been proposed to model the time-dependent deformation of rocks. The existing constitutive models can be classified into two groups: 1) Classical creep models based on a network of many components of springs, dashpots and sliders which interact by sharing the applied load (Nishihara 1952; Boukharov et al. 1995; Davy et al. 1995; Ranalli 1995; Zhou et al. 2011; Jiang et al. 2013; Yang et al. 2014), and 2) Empirical damage models in forms of power laws or exponential laws which are able to describe the experimentally obtained strain-time behavior (Zhang et al. 1999; Zhang et al. 2004, Main, 2000; Amitrano and Helmstetter, 2006). The classical creep models are normally based on a combination of standard elements such as the Kelvin element, Maxwell element, Newtonian dashpot and the Hooke spring (Boukharov et al. 1995; Davy et al. 1995; Ranalli, 1995; Jiang et al. 2013). The multi-component creep models can comprise of simple linear models and complex nonlinear models. These simple linear models which include the linear superposition of a small number of viscous and elastic elements, such as the linear Burger model (Ranalli, 1995), cannot describe the final creep stage of nonlinear, unstable accelerating creep due to the progressive accumulation of cracks in the final stages. Complex nonlinear models, which contain large numbers of Newtonian elastic and viscous elements (Davy et al. 1995), non-linear dashpot (Boukharov et al. 1995), fractional derivative Abel dashpot (Zhou et al. 2011), are capable of predicting the nonlinearity at the tertiary creep. However, these models are very complicated, and it is difficult to obtain the large number of model parameters based on limited experimental data. In most of these models, the strain is decomposed into two or more components which are represented by linear, viscous and nonlinear elements (Jiang et al. 2013; Yang et al. 2014). The strain partitioning is purely for the convenience of better predicting the time-dependent deformation, and usually does not have any theoretical basis.

The empirical damage models which establish the relationship between creep strain and time based on the experimental data are proposed in forms of exponential laws and power laws (Zhang et al. 1999; Zhang et al. 2004, Main, 2000; Amitrano and Helmstetter, 2006). These models assume that the creep phenomenon is associated with the progressive crack accumulation in the rock during loading. Damage mechanics is introduced in these models to account for the time-dependent crack growth. Amitrano and Helmstetter (2006) proposed a numerical model to predict the creep deformation of rocks which employs different forms of exponential or power laws for the primary creep, secondary creep and tertiary creep. Main (2000) proposed a power-law hybrid

model which decomposes the total strain into the transient creep strain dominating the primary stage and the accelerating creep strain controlling the tertiary stage.

In summary, due to the complex inherent features of the creep behavior, the existing creep models either predict the strain evolution using different forms of empirical equations for different creep stages (Wang 2004; Amitrano and Helmstetter 2006) or by decomposing the total strain into several strain components (Boukharov et al. 1995; Main 2000; Jiang et al. 2013; Chen et al. 2014; Yang et al. 2014). For instance, Main (2000) decomposes the total creep strain into transient creep strain and the accelerating creep strain, and Jiang et al. (2013) decomposes the total strain into elastic strain ϵ_e , viscoelastic strain ϵ_{ve} , and viscoplastic strain ϵ_{vp} . These models inevitably require many parameters, which further makes the models difficult to implement and use. Katsuki and Gutierrez (2011) proposed a single equation without strain partitioning to predict the time-dependent deformation of asphalt concrete. Despite its simplicity and easy implementation, Katsuki and Gutierrez (2011)'s model is restricted only by its lack of ability of predicting the failure time and closely representing the strain evolution.

The phenomena such as an increase of hydraulic permeability and dilatancy, a decrease of elastic modulus, and the evolution of the accumulated acoustic emission, are observed during creep experiments (Lockner 1993; Main 2000; Amitrano and Helmstetter 2006; Heap et al. 2009). In turn, creep phenomena are due to time-dependent microcrack propagation and coalescence which occur under applied constant pressure. Hence, the creep deformation can be described by damage mechanics with the damage variable varying with time, as supported by the AE (acoustic emission) observation from the creep tests on sandstone by Heap et al. (2009). Fig. 2 shows that the experimentally obtained AE in sandstone which represents the damage process (Heap et al. 2009) is closely correlated with the creep stain behavior. From this point of view, it is reasonable to propose that the creep behavior can be predicted given that a proper damage evolution law is used.

Fig. 2 Relationships between axial strain vs. time, and cumulative AE energy vs. time for sandstone. (a) differential stress=132 MPa; (b) differential stress =141 MPa. Experimental data from Heap et al. (2009).

In most cases, the creep behavior clearly shows a steady secondary stage, i.e. the experimental results in Fig. 2a. However, for some cases, the secondary stage is not always observed and there is rather a crossover between decreasing primary creep and accelerating tertiary creep than the stationary creep stage (Lockner, 1993). For instance, in the above experimental results in Fig. 2b, the secondary creep stage does not appear clearly. Nevertheless, the secondary creep stage can be treated as the transition between primary and tertiary creep (Main 2000) no matter it clearly appears or not.

Hence, the whole creep behavior can be modelled by partitioning it into two sections by introducing a concept of transition time t_m (see Fig. 1). The secondary creep before t_m is treated as the extension of the primary creep phase while the secondary creep after t_m is regarded as the beginning of the tertiary creep phase, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

This paper proposes a simple creep model to predict the long-term deformation of rocks. Damage mechanics is introduced in the model to describe the time-dependent progressive crack accumulation. The time-dependent damage evolution is described in the forms of an exponential function and a power law for the two sections defined by the transition time t_m . The model is based on experimental data on sandstone and granite, and are validated against results from the creep tests on sandstone.

2. Creep Model

The proposed 3-D creep model is presented in this section. The relationship between the nominal stress tensor σ_{ij} and the effective stress tensor σ'_{ij} , which governs the constitutive behavior of the rock, is expressed as follows:

$$\sigma_{ij} = \sigma'_{ij}(1 - D) \quad (1)$$

where $i = 1,2,3$ and D is the scalar damage variable.

$$\sigma'_{ij} = C_{ijkl}\varepsilon'_{kl} \quad (2)$$

where C_{ijkl} are the components of elastic stiffness tensor; ε'_{kl} are the effective strain tensor.

The Lemaitre strain equivalence assumption indicates that the nominal strain tensor ε_{ij} is equal to the effective strain tensor ε'_{ij} :

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \varepsilon'_{ij} \quad (3)$$

Substituting Eqs. (2) and (3) into Eq. (1), one has the following constitutive equation:

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl}\varepsilon_{ij}(1 - D) \quad (4)$$

Assuming that the media is isotropic and homogeneous, the stiffness tensor can be written as:

$$C_{ijkl} = K\delta_{ij}\delta_{kl} + G(\delta_{ik}\delta_{jl} + \delta_{il}\delta_{jk} - \frac{2}{3}\delta_{ij}\delta_{kl}) \quad (5)$$

and the constitutive Eq. (4) can be rewritten as:

$$\sigma_{ij} = K\delta_{ij}\varepsilon_{kk}(1 - D) + 2G(1 - D)(\varepsilon_{ij} - \frac{1}{3}\delta_{ij}\varepsilon_{kk}) \quad (6)$$

where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta; K the bulk modulus; G the shear modulus; and ε_{kk} the first invariant of the strain tensor equal to the volumetric strain.

The strain tensor can also be expressed as a function of the stresses as:

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{qK(1-D)}\delta_{ij}\sigma_{kk} + \frac{1}{2G(1-D)}(\sigma_{ij} - \frac{\sigma_{kk}}{3}\delta_{ij}) \quad (7)$$

where σ_{kk} is the mean hydrostatic stress and can be related to the volumetric strain as $\sigma_{kk} = 3K\varepsilon_{kk}$.

It is assumed in this study that the first component of the left side of Eq. (7), which is associated with the hydrostatic stress and volumetric response, is time-independent. On the other hand, the second component, which causes the distortional deformation, is time-dependent (Pan and Dong 1991). Hence, Eq. (7) can be simplified to be:

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{S_{ij}}{2G(1-D)}(\sigma_{ij} - \frac{\sigma_{kk}}{3}\delta_{ij}) \quad (8)$$

where $S_{ij} = \sigma_{ij} - \frac{\sigma_{kk}}{3}\delta_{ij}$ is the deviatoric stress tensor.

The derivative of the strain tensor with respect to time is expressed as:

$$d\varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{S_{ij}}{2G(1-D)^2}dDdt \quad (9)$$

In case of conventional triaxial compression test

$$\sigma_2 = \sigma_3 \quad (10)$$

$$\text{and } S_{11} = \frac{2}{3}(\sigma_1 - \sigma_3) \quad (11)$$

Substituting Eqs. (10) and (11) into Eq. (9), the incremental axial creep strain can be expressed as:

$$d\varepsilon_{11} = \frac{\sigma_1 - \sigma_3}{3G(1-D)^2}dDdt \quad (12)$$

Time to failure t_f and transition time t_m

A typical strain-time curve is divided into two sections: $t \leq t_m$ and $t_m < t \leq t_f$ (see Fig. 1). t_f is the failure time. In this study, the transition time t_m is simply defined as:

$$t_m = \frac{2}{3}t_f \quad (13)$$

The time to failure can be estimated by a power law (Amitrano and Helmstetter 2006):

$$t_f = t_0 \left(\frac{q}{q_0}\right)^{-b} \quad (14)$$

where q is the deviatoric stress and $q = \sigma_1 - \sigma_3$ for triaxial tests and q_0 is the instantaneous shear strength. The instantaneous shear strength q_0 can be obtained according to Mohr-Coulomb criterion. The constants t_0 and b are associated with rock properties and the conditions which the rocks are subjected to. The capability of Eq. (14) in predicting the failure time t_f of the creep response is indicated by the comparison between Eq. (14) and experimentally observed data on

granite and sandstone (see Fig. 3). The determined parameters of Eq. (14) for various tests are shown in Table 1. Note that in Fig. 3, most of the experimental data are from granite with only one set of sandstone data. This, however, does not affect the applicability of Eq. (14) in sandstone. The creep model proposed in the following section will be verified by experimental data on sandstone.

Fig. 3 Comparisons between Eq. (14) and the experimental data. Solid lines are model predictions. Experimental data for Barre granite are from Kranz (1980); Quartz from Scholz (1972); Indiana granite from Masuda (2001); and Darley Dale sandstone from Baud and Meredith (1997).

Table 1 Parameters a and b of Eq. (14) for various rocks.

Parameters	t_0	b
Barre granite $\sigma_3 = 0.1$ MPa Kranz (1980)	50	30
Quartz $\sigma_3 = 0$ MPa Scholz (1972)	20	60
Indiana granite $\sigma_3 = 50$ Mpa Masuda (2001)	0.1	55
Barre granite $\sigma_3 = 53$ MPa Kranz (1980)	60	50
Darley Dale sandstone $\sigma'_3 = 25$ MPa Baud and Meredith (1997)	390	24

Damage evolution

Damage mechanics is introduced in the proposed model to account for the fact that creep and other aspects of rock behavior originate from damage due to growth in the microcracks in the rock during loading. It is assumed that the damage variable D have different evolution forms for $t \leq$

t_m and $t_m < t \leq t_f$. The following equations are proposed to describe the damage evolution for the two sections.

For the first section $t \leq t_m$, the damage D evolution is expressed by:

$$D = 1 - e^{-\alpha_1 t^\beta} \text{ when } t \leq t_m \quad (15a)$$

Its derivative to time is obtained:

$$\frac{\partial D}{\partial t} = \alpha_1 \beta t^{\beta-1} e^{-\alpha_1 t^\beta} \quad (15b)$$

For the second section $t_m < t \leq t_f$, the damage D evolution is expressed by:

$$D = \left(\frac{t_f - t_m}{t_f - t} \right)^{\alpha_2} \text{ when } t_m < t \leq t_f \quad (16a)$$

Its derivative to time is obtained:

$$\frac{\partial D}{\partial t} = \alpha_2 (t_f - t_m)^{\alpha_2} (t_f - t)^{-\alpha_2 - 1} \quad (16b)$$

At time t_m , the derivative of Eq. (15a) is equal to that of Eq. (16a). Hence, the parameter α_2 can be expressed in the other parameters:

$$\alpha_2 = \alpha_1 \beta t^{\beta-1} e^{-\alpha_1 t^\beta} (t_f - t_m) \quad (17)$$

This means that number of parameters is reduced by one, and now there are only three required model parameters which are α_1 , β and t_f .

3. Verification of the proposed model

The verification of the proposed model is carried out in this section. The model is verified using the results of creep tests on water-saturated sandstone performed by Heap et al. (2009), and Jiang et al. (2013).

Firstly, Heap et al. (2009)'s three creep tests on sandstones under the constant deviatoric stresses of 125, 132 and 141 MPa are modelled. The failure time of the three tests is predicted using Eq. (14) with the determined parameters of $t_0 = 0.00027$ and $b=57$. The comparison shown in Fig. 4 indicates that the proposed model can represent the characteristics of failure time.

The parameters for the damage model α_1 , β and t_f are obtained by least-square fitting the curve to the experimental data and shown in Table 2. The time-dependent strain variations for the three creep tests are predicted using the proposed model. Fig. 5 shows the comparison between the model predicted creep curve and the experimentally observed data. It can be seen that the proposed model is capable of closely representing the three-stage time-dependent creep behavior of rocks.

Table 2 The parameters of the damage model for Heap et al. (2009)'s tests on sandstone.

Parameters	α_1	β	$t_f, mins$
$\sigma_1 - \sigma_3 = 141 \text{ MPa}$	0.85	0.45	10.6
$\sigma_1 - \sigma_3 = 132 \text{ MPa}$	0.17	0.3	160
$\sigma_1 - \sigma_3 = 125 \text{ MPa}$	0.17	0.3	362

Fig. 4. Comparison of experimentally obtained failure times and the model.

Fig. 5 Strain-time curves of sandstone subjected to varying constant stresses. (a) 141 MPa; (b) 132 MPa; and (c) 125 MPa.

Jiang et al. (2013)'s creep test on sandstone under stress-stepping loading and the confining stress of 6 MPa is used to provide the second set of verification of the proposed model. The experimentally obtained creep strain vs. time relationship under stress-stepping loading is shown in Fig. 6. The creep strain vs. time relationships of sandstone subjected to various constant stresses (see Fig. 7) are obtained by applying the Boltzmann superposition approach to the stress-stepping strain-time curve (Mijovic 1994; Jiang et al. 2013). It can be seen from Fig. 7 that the strain-time curves for the first five constant stress levels of 5, 15, 25, 35 and 45 MPa do not have the accelerating creep phase and only the curve for 55 MPa shows the complete three creep phases.

The creep curves for stress levels of 5, 15, 25 MPa are almost straight, which means that no creep occurs under these stress levels which are much lower than the peak deviatoric stress of 126.6 MPa. Creep effects start to show up since the stress level of 35 MPa and become prominent at 45 MPa.

Fig. 6 Strain-time curves of Jiang et al. (2013)'s test on sandstone under stress-stepping loading.

Fig. 7 Strain-time curves of Jiang et al. (2013)'s test on sandstone subjected to various constant stresses.

Yang et al. (2014) also pointed out that there exists a creep threshold stress. Creep deformation does not occur below stress levels lower than the creep threshold and the induced strain can be computed by the elastic relationship. The model proposed by Yang et al. (2014) is a three-component creep model which decomposes the total strain into elastic strain represented by the Hooke body, the transient creep strain represented by the Schiffman body, and the visco-plastic strain by the nonlinear visco-plastic body. In addition, Yang et al. (2014)'s model includes different forms of equations for different stress levels (Fig. 6), which makes the already complicated component creep model even more complicated. The following will show that the proposed model in this study does not need to vary the forms of equations in order to predict the stress-dependent creep behavior.

Fig. 8. Creep characteristic curves under different stress levels. After Yang et al. (2014).

The proposed model is used to predict the creep strain behavior and the damage model parameters are determined and shown in Table 3. For stress levels of 5, 15, 25 MPa under which no creep occurs, the parameters α_1 and β are given very small values and t_f an extremely large value (any other random large values will work). For stress levels of 35 and 45 MPa under which creep deformation starts to appear (see the beginning part of the creep curves in Fig. 7), but without the tertiary creep, α_1 and β are determined by the curve-fitting technique whereas t_f is given a

random value larger than the one used for 55 MPa. For stress level of 55 MPa, the parameters are obtained by the curve-fitting technique. The comparisons between experiment and the model are shown in Figs. 6 and 7 for stress-stepping loading and various stress levels, respectively. It can be seen that the proposed model is able to predict the creep strain behavior under stress-stepping loading. Moreover, the proposed model is capable of predicting the elastic behavior without the need to change the equation forms according to the stress levels. This feature makes the proposed model much simpler and easy to implement.

Except for the intrinsic rock property parameters, such as shear modulus G , Young's Modulus E and Poisson's ratio ν , there are only four parameters α_1 , β and t_f (t_0, b) required in the proposed model. The parameters will reduce to three if the failure time is given and the failure time equation is not used. The proposed model is simple as it is based on the mechanism which assumes that the time-dependent deformation is solely driven by the damage evolution.

Table 3 The parameters of the damage model for Jiang et al. (2013)'s test on sandstone.

Parameters	α_1	β	$t_f, mins$
$\sigma_1 - \sigma_3 = 5$ MPa	0.005	0.005	1e5
$\sigma_1 - \sigma_3 = 15$ MPa	0.005	0.005	1e5
$\sigma_1 - \sigma_3 = 25$ MPa	0.005	0.005	1e5
$\sigma_1 - \sigma_3 = 35$ MPa	0.1	0.2	1000
$\sigma_1 - \sigma_3 = 45$ MPa	0.15	0.2	700
$\sigma_1 - \sigma_3 = 55$ MPa	0.3	0.5	37

4. Conclusions

A simple creep model is proposed in this study to describe the three-stage creep deformation of rocks under conventional triaxial loading conditions. The creep experimental observations associate the time-dependent creep behavior with the damage process due to propagation of microcracks in the rocks with time under applied constant stress. This damage evolution associated with phenomena such as an increase of hydraulic permeability and the evolution of the accumulated acoustic emission. It is reasonable to assume that the creep strain with time varying rates can be solely described by the damage mechanics, without the need to use strain partitioning or to establish model equations respectively for the different creep phrases.

The proposed model is verified by creep tests carried out on sandstones under constant stresses as well as stress-stepping loading. The comparisons between the model and the creep tests show that the proposed model agrees well with the experimentally observed data. The model is able to reflect the three-phase creep behavior under higher stress levels as well as the elastic behavior under lower stress levels using the same model equations. **The model was based on experimental data on sandstone and granite and were validated against results from the creep tests on sandstone.**

The main features of the proposed model include: 1) Simple mathematical form as it contains only one strain component without strain partitioning, and one set of equations to predict the creep deformation for all stress levels; and 2) The model requires only four parameters. All these features make the proposed model simple to use and easy to implement.

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